

Space Resource Utilisation in European Context: Policies, Programmes, and Planning for the Next Decade. E. Shashkova¹, A. Chronopoulos¹, T. Jones¹, L. Petzold¹, S. Schubert¹. ¹European Space Policy Institute (Schwarzenbergplatz 16/Top 1, 1010 Vienna, Austria, elizaveta.shashkova@espi.eu).

Context: Space Resource Utilisation (SRU) has long been viewed as a fanciful economic investment by a handful of space powers and private companies. Recent global signals have indicated a shift in lunar exploration and funding priorities, with SRU now taking a prominent role in the substantially increased lunar mission cadences of the U.S. and China, with interest in lunar exploration from 61 Artemis Accords signatories and 13 International Lunar Research Station national signatories, plus private sector SRU-focused companies from Belgium, China, France, Germany, Israel, Japan, Luxembourg, Poland, U.K., and U.S.. This potential has reverberated through supranational organizations, resulting in the creation of a U.N. Action Team on Lunar Activities Consultation and Space Resources Working Group [1], and the declaration of the Moon as “strategic infrastructure” by ESA Director General Josef Aschbacher at the February 2026 Munich Security Conference [2].

National policies, programmes, and plans are beginning to incorporate SRU with this uptick in lunar exploration interest. SRU is central to the implementation of a permanently-inhabited lunar bases and of a sustainable circular space economy allowing further exploration and science, and also fuels prospects for profitability through sale of He-3 and rare Earth materials on Earth as well as the potential for lunar data centers. In order to understand the potential of SRU in a European context, it is critical to examine national rhetoric and investments related to lunar exploration, as well as the breadth of commercial investment in the sector.

Objective: This presentation aims at examining the evolution of Europe’s positioning on the topic of SRU in the past years, through an holistic approach combining perspectives from policy, commercial, and programmatic domains.

Methodology: For each sector, relevant items has been identified and mapped as follows:

Sector	Items mapped and analysed
Policy	National space and resources strategies, national laws, international binding and non-binding agreements, standards, party manifestos, submissions to the Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (COPUOS), international bilateral/multilateral agreements

Commercial	Companies, investments and forecasts
Programmes	Space agencies programmes and roadmaps, tenders, academic publications

The analysis of each type of followed an adapted methodology to understand the relative importance of SRU within the corresponding sector and its specifics, such as the type of resource and activity, the origin, the market addressed and the narrative it follows. When applicable the results of the European mapping are compared to the ones of the main current space powers. This approach allows to highlight strategic opportunities for European engagement in SRU over the coming decade, and areas for potential cooperation and competition.

Discussion: Mention of space has substantially increased in European policy and strategy in the last five years, however, lunar exploration and SRU remains a minor focus, with nine European nations and three non-European nations mentioning SRU. Technology roadmaps from a handful of major space agencies exist incorporating SRU: ASA, CNES, CNSA, ESA, JAXA, NASA, and UKSA. The Luxembourg Space Agency and Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology also funds an entire research centre, the European Space Resources Innovation Centre, in strategic partnership with ESA. Academic interest is increasing in SRU policy, with over 100 publications on the subject.

Very few European tenders exist, though SRU companies have sprung up in Belgium, France, Germany, Luxembourg, and Poland; the U.S., in contrast has approximately 200 tenders and a broad lunar ecosystem, while Japan and China also have substantial SRU technological investments at both public and private levels. The majority of planned missions through 2029 with resource objectives target the lunar south pole due to expected water ice deposits and the volatile-rich permanently shadowed regions. They are largely focused on prospecting, mapping, and characterisation in a nascent stage of SRU technology development, and are focused on testing technologies such as drilling, volatile extraction, oxygen production, and regolith-based construction rather than lunar mining. The narrative surrounding most missions is as an enabler for sustained exploration (e.g., fuel, life support, construction materials) rather than immediate commercial export.

This presentation further highlights by nation states evolving positions on SRU from policy, commercial, and programmatic domains.

References: [1] Report of the Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space 67th session, Aug. 30, 2024; [2] Wall, Robert, “ESA Boss Couches Lunar Plans In Security Terms”, Aviation Week, 16 Feb 2026 <https://aviationweek.com/space/budget-policy-regulation/esa-boss-couches-lunar-plans-security-terms>